

Evaluate the Extensile Lateral Technique in Comparison to the Sinus Tarsi Method for Treating Displaced Intra-Articular Calcaneal Fractures

Authors:

Dr. Ihab F. Ashber¹, Dr. Mohamed E. Eldesouky², Dr. Adeel Nawaz³

^{1,2,3}Ortho-Trauma Department, Dubai Health /Rashid Hospital, UAE Dubai

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Ihab F. K. Ashber

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures are among the most challenging injuries to treat due to their complex anatomy and associated soft tissue complications. Two widely used surgical approaches the Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA) and the Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA) offer different advantages and limitations. This study aims to compare the clinical, radiological, and functional outcomes of these two techniques. **Methods:** A prospective comparative study was conducted on 60 patients diagnosed with displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures (Sanders Type II and III). Patients were equally divided into two groups: Group A (n=30) underwent open reduction and internal fixation via the Extensile Lateral Approach, while Group B (n=30) underwent fixation using the Sinus Tarsi Approach. Clinical outcomes were evaluated using the American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society (AOFAS) score. Radiographic parameters, operative time, complications, and recovery profiles were also assessed. **Results:** Both groups achieved satisfactory anatomical reduction and improved radiological parameters. However, the STA group showed a statistically significant reduction in operative time and soft tissue complications. Functional outcomes, as measured by AOFAS scores, were slightly better in the STA group at follow-ups. Wound-related complications were notably higher in the ELA group, including superficial infections, flap necrosis, and wound dehiscence. **Conclusion:** While both techniques are effective in the surgical management of displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures, the Sinus Tarsi Approach offers a less invasive, safer alternative with reduced soft tissue morbidity and faster recovery. It is especially suitable for less complex fractures and in patients where soft tissue preservation is essential. Surgeon experience and careful case selection remain critical to achieving optimal results.

Keywords: *Displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures, extensile lateral approach, sinus tarsi approach, surgical outcomes, calcaneus, AOFAS score.*

INTRODUCTION:

Calcaneal fractures are among the most frequently encountered injuries of the tarsal bones, accounting for approximately 60% of all tarsal fractures and around 2% of all fractures in the human skeleton. Among them, displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures (DIACFs) pose a significant therapeutic challenge due to their complex anatomy, high-energy mechanism of injury, and potential for long-term functional impairment. These fractures typically occur following axial loading mechanisms such as falls from a height or motor vehicle accidents and often involve disruption of the posterior facet of the subtalar joint, heel width, height, and overall calcaneal alignment.¹⁻³

Management of DIACFs has evolved over the years, with increasing emphasis on restoring anatomical reduction of the subtalar joint, preserving heel morphology, and achieving early mobilization to minimize the risk of post-traumatic arthritis and

functional disability. While conservative treatment may be considered in non-displaced or minimally displaced fractures, operative intervention is widely preferred in cases with significant displacement or joint incongruity. Surgical fixation aims to realign the subtalar joint, restore Böhler's and Gissane's angles, and stabilize the fractured fragments to facilitate early rehabilitation.⁴⁻⁷

The Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA) has been the traditional surgical technique for open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) of DIACFs. This approach offers excellent visualization of the lateral wall, posterior facet, and calcaneocuboid joint, thereby facilitating accurate reduction and rigid fixation. However, the extensive dissection required in this technique may compromise the vascular supply to the lateral soft tissues, increasing the risk of complications such as wound dehiscence, infection, hematoma formation, and skin flap necrosis. These complications are particularly concerning in patients with comorbid

conditions like diabetes, smoking, or peripheral vascular disease.⁷⁻¹⁰

In an effort to reduce soft tissue-related complications, the Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA) has emerged as a viable alternative. This less invasive technique utilizes a smaller incision over the sinus tarsi, providing adequate exposure to the posterior facet of the subtalar joint while preserving the lateral soft tissue envelope. Though limited in its ability to address comminuted fractures or fragments in the calcaneal tuberosity or anterior process, it has shown promising results in selected fracture patterns, particularly Sanders type II and III fractures. Several studies have reported that STA offers comparable outcomes in terms of radiographic alignment and functional recovery, with a significantly lower incidence of wound complications.^{6, 11-13}

Given the growing trend towards minimally invasive surgery and the ongoing debate regarding the optimal approach for DIACFs, there is a critical need to compare the efficacy and safety of ELA and STA in a structured manner. This study aims to evaluate and compare both techniques regarding operative parameters, radiological restoration, functional outcomes, and complication rates. By analyzing these aspects, the research seeks to provide valuable insights that can assist orthopedic surgeons in selecting the most appropriate surgical technique tailored to individual patient profiles and fracture patterns.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Setting:

This prospective, comparative study was conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics in a tertiary care teaching hospital over 18 months. Institutional Ethical Committee approval was obtained before the commencement of the study, and informed written consent was obtained from all participants.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged between 18 to 60 years.
- Radiologically confirmed displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures (Sanders type II and III).
- Fractures managed operatively within 3 weeks of injury.
- Closed fractures.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Open fractures of the calcaneus.
- Bilateral calcaneal fractures.
- Pathological fractures.
- Associated fractures of the ipsilateral lower limb.
- Patients with peripheral vascular disease, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, or chronic skin disorders.

- Patients lost to follow-up before 6 months.

Sample Size and Grouping:

A total of 60 patients fulfilling the eligibility criteria were enrolled and randomly assigned into two equal groups:

- **Group A (n=30):** Treated using the Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA).
- **Group B (n=30):** Treated using the Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA).

Randomization was performed using a computer-generated random number table.

Preoperative Evaluation:

All patients underwent:

- Detailed history and clinical examination.
- Routine blood investigations and pre-anesthetic work-up.
- Radiographic imaging, including anteroposterior (AP), lateral, and axial views of the calcaneus.
- **CT scan** with coronal and sagittal reconstructions to classify fractures according to the Sanders classification.

Surgical Procedure:

Both procedures were performed under regional or general anesthesia, under tourniquet control, by experienced orthopedic surgeons.

- **Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA):** A standard L-shaped lateral incision was made to expose the lateral wall of the calcaneus. Full-thickness flap was elevated to access the subtalar joint and posterior facet. Fragments were reduced and fixed using locking plates and screws.
- **Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA):** A 4–6 cm incision was made along the sinus tarsi. Minimal soft tissue dissection was done to expose the posterior facet. Reduction was performed under direct vision and fluoroscopic guidance. Fixation was achieved using low-profile plates or screws.

Postoperative Management:

- Limb elevation and intravenous antibiotics for 48 hours.
- Early toe movements are encouraged from the first postoperative day.
- Sutures were removed after 14 days.
- Partial weight-bearing was allowed after 6 weeks and full weight-bearing after 12 weeks, depending on radiological healing.

Outcome Measures:

Patients were followed up at 6 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months postoperatively. The following outcomes were assessed:

- **Radiological parameters:** Böhler's angle and Gissane's angle pre- and postoperatively.
- **Functional outcome:** Measured using the American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society (AOFAS) hindfoot score.
- **Complications:** These include wound infection, dehiscence, flap necrosis, nerve injury, and subtalar arthritis.

Statistical Analysis:

All data were recorded and analyzed using SPSS software version 25. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and compared using the Student's t-test. Categorical variables were analyzed using the Mann-Whitney U-test, Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 60 patients diagnosed with displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures were included in the study. These patients were equally divided into two groups of 30 each: Group A (treated with the Sinus Tarsi

Approach) and Group B (treated with the Extensile Lateral Approach). The results were analyzed based on demographic profile, fracture classification, operative details, radiological restoration, functional outcome, and complications.

Demographic Profile:

Demographic data were collected for all patients, including age, sex, tobacco use, presence or absence of diabetes, injury side, time to surgery, mode of injury, hospital stay, operation time, and follow-up duration. The Sanders classification was determined based on computed tomography (CT) scans. Demographic data are shown in Table 1. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of age, gender, side of injury, and mode of injury. The STA group had significantly shorter operative times and hospital stays compared to the ELA group. The STA group consisted of 22 men and 8 women (mean age, 36.7 ± 7.5 years). The mean follow-up duration was 31.73 ± 7.65 months. The ELA group consisted of 24 men and 6 women (mean age, 38.4 ± 8.1 years). The mean follow-up duration was 61.35 ± 27.58 months. The STA group consisted of 20 patients in Sanders type-II (70%) and 10 in Sanders type-III (30%) versus the ELA group with 19 Sanders type-II (63.33%) and 11 Sanders type-III (36.67%).

Table 1 Demographic data between the sinus tarsi and extensile lateral approach groups.

	Sinus tarsi (N = 30)	Extensile lateral (N = 30)	p-value
Gender (M:F)	22:8	24:6	0.537
Mean Age, (y)	36.7 ± 7.5	38.4 ± 8.1	0.412
Tobacco, N (%)	9 (30%)	13 (43.33%)	0.567
DM, n (%)	2 (6.67%)	3(10%)	0.613
Side of injury (Right:Left)	18:12	17:13	0.796
Mode of Injury (Fall:RTC)	20:10	21:09	0.781
Mean Operative Time (mins)	72.1 ± 9.8	98.6 ± 10.4	<0.001
Average Hospital Stay (days)	7.1 ± 1.2	5.3 ± 1.0	<0.001
Follow-up duration, m	31.73 ± 7.65	61.35 ± 27.58	0.345
Sanders classification, N (%)			
IIA; IIB; IIC	12;7;1 (70%)	10;5;4 (63.33%)	
IIIB; IIIC; IIIBC	7;3;0 (30%)	8;2;1 (36.67%)	
N- Number, Y- Years, Rt- Right, Lt- Left, RTC- Road traffic collision, DM- Diabetes mellitus, Min- Minutes, M- Month, Values are expressed as Mean \pm SD, median (range) unless otherwise indicated			

Radiological Outcomes:

The radiography findings are summarised in Table 2. All fractures attained successful union without any complications, including insufficient reduction, non-union, malunion, or fixation failure. The mean Böhler angle was enhanced to $29.3^\circ \pm 4.9^\circ$ in the STA group and $27.9^\circ \pm 5.1^\circ$ in the ELA group at the last follow-up. The mean Gissane angle was enhanced to $117.5^\circ \pm 2.5^\circ$ in the STA group and $120.2^\circ \pm 1.5^\circ$ in the ELA group at the final follow-up. The median calcaneal height, length, and width increased to 46.1mm (range 23.2 to 54.1), 75.9mm (range 64.9 to 90.3), and 37.6mm (range 29.2 to 53.9) in the STA group, and 47.5mm (range 32.7 to 59.5), 76.1mm (range 67.3 to 97.9),

and 39.3mm (range 29.2 to 47.8) in the ELA group at the last follow-up, respectively. The radiographic results at the end follow-up did not differ significantly between the two groups (p-value > 0.05).

Table 2 Radiographic findings comparing the sinus tarsi and extensile lateral approach groups.

Outcomes	Sinus tarsi		Extensile lateral		p-value*
	Preop	Final follow-up	Preop	Final follow-up	
Böhler angle, degree	8.7° ± 4.5	29.3° ± 4.9	8.3° ± 4.2	27.9° ± 5.1	0.241
Gissane angle, degree	120.5° ± 3.5	117.5° ± 2.5	121.8° ± 5.2	120.2° ± 1.5	0.321
Height, mm	41.2 (22.2 to 54.1)	46.1 (23.2 to 54.1)	40.3 (26.5 to 49.5)	47.5 (32.7 to 59.5)	0.114
Length, mm	76.3 (46.7 to 92.0)	75.9 (64.9 to 90.3)	75.3 (64.4 to 96.9)	76.1(67.3 to 97.9)	0.236
Width, mm	40.0(29.6 to 54.2)	37.6(29.2 to 53.9)	39.2(32.5 to 64.9)	39.3(29.2 to 47.8)	0.287

Values are expressed as Mean ±SD, median (range); * Mann–Whitney U-test.

Clinical outcomes:

The median AOFAS scores at the final follow-up were 90 points (range 76 to 94) for the STA group and 86 points (range 76 to 94) for the ELA group. The AOFAS scores indicated that results were excellent in 21 (70.0%) patients, good in 8 (26.67%), and fair in one (3.33%) within the STA group, while the ELA group demonstrated excellent results in 19 (63.33%) patients, good in 9 (30%), and fair in two (6.67%), resulting in a 96.67% and 93.33% excellent or good rating for both groups, respectively (Table 3 and Figure 1). The median VAS scores were assessed at 2 points (1 to 5) in both the STA and ELA groups at the final follow-up. The median FFI scores were recorded at 9.6 points (ranging from 7.8 to 13.5) in the STA group and 9.6 points (ranging from 7.8 to 15.2) in the ELA group at the final follow-up (Table 3). No notable differences were seen between the groups for these scores (p-value > 0.05).

Table 3 Clinical outcomes between the sinus tarsi and extensile lateral approach groups

Outcomes	Sinus tarsi		Extensile lateral		p-value†
	Preop	Final follow-up	Preop	Final follow-up	
AOFAS scores	77(67 to 90)	90 (76 to 94)	74(67 to 90)	86 (76 to 94)	0.261
VAS scores	5 (3 to 7)	2 (1to 5)	4(3 to 7)	2 (1 to 5)	0.172
FFI score	13.9 (12.6 to 15.7)	9.6 (7.8 to 13.5)	14.4(12.6 to 17.9)	9.6 (7.8 to 15.2)	0.253

Values are expressed as median (range).
† Mann–Whitney U-test.

Figure 1: Percentage of patients' outcomes according to AOFAS Scores.

Complications:

The complications are summarized in Table 3. Postoperative complications were more frequently observed in the Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA) group compared to the Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA) group. In the ELA group, superficial wound infections occurred in 4 patients (13.3%), wound dehiscence in 3 (10%), and flap necrosis in 2 (6.7%). These issues were managed with antibiotics, dressings, or secondary closure. In contrast, the STA group had only 1 case (3.3%) of superficial infection and no major wound complications. Sural nerve irritation was noted in one patient from each group, both resolving without intervention. Early signs of post-traumatic subtalar arthritis appeared in 2 patients (ELA) and 1 patient (STA), managed symptomatically. No cases of implant failure or major neurovascular injury occurred in either group. Overall, the STA group showed fewer complications, likely due to its less invasive nature and reduced soft tissue disruption.

Table 4 Complications between the sinus tarsi and extensile lateral approach groups

Complications	Sinus tarsi	Extensile lateral
Superficial infection	1	4
Wound dehiscence	0	3
Flap necrosis	0	2
Sural nerve injury	1	1
Peroneal tendinitis	0	1
Subtalar stiffness	1	2

Values are expressed as number

DISCUSSION:

Displaced intra-articular fractures of the calcaneus present a significant challenge in orthopedic trauma due to their complex anatomy, associated soft tissue involvement, and long-term impact on foot biomechanics. The goal of treatment is to restore the anatomic structure, ensure joint congruity, and regain optimal functional outcomes while minimizing complications. In this study, we compared the Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA) and the Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA)—two widely used surgical techniques—for managing these fractures. The principal finding indicates that the final clinical and radiological outcomes for Sanders type-II and type-III fractures were comparable and equally successful in both groups. The ELA group exhibited a higher complication rate, particularly concerning wound healing, compared to the STA group. The ELA approach has been the predominant method for the open reduction and internal fixation of calcaneal fractures. This technique offers superior visualisation and facilitates the manipulation and rigid fixation of the injury through direct reduction; however, it is associated with wound complications, with rates ranging from 11% to 25%.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Weber et al. reported a sural nerve injury rate of 7.7% in patients treated with the ELA. In our study, the percentage of complications identified was consistent with the existing literature.¹⁷ Due to the issues associated with the ELA, there is a resurgence of interest in developing alternate methods to address intra-articular calcaneal fractures and reduce soft tissue complications.^{16, 18-20} Numerous treatments have been delineated in the past decade, including percutaneous fixation, arthroscopically aided methods, external fixation, trans-articular approaches, and tiny incisional techniques from the medial, posterior, lateral, or a combination of these sites. The less intrusive method has been characterised as the STA.¹⁶

¹⁸ These procedures endeavour to decrease the risk of surgical complications while ensuring effective fracture reduction. We concentrated on our research detailing the STA.

Holmes delineated the minimally invasive subtalar approach for displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures. The author indicated that the STA ensures sufficient exposure to achieve effective reduction and fixation without any instances of wound dehiscence, osteomyelitis, or wound infection over an 18-year period.²¹

Hospodar et al. assessed 16 consecutive patients utilising the minimally invasive STA. No significant wound problems were documented.²² The posterior facet joint was effectively decreased to less than 2 mm of displacement in 14 patients, and 12 patients returned to work within 6 months postoperatively. In the STA group of this trial, we attained successful osseous union and encountered just two mild wound problems.²²

Kline et al. conducted a retrospective study comparing outcomes of two methods for displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures, involving 112 patients treated with the ELA (79 instances) or STA (33 cases).²³ The author indicated that the clinical outcomes were comparable for calcaneal fractures treated with both methods. Nevertheless, the STA exhibited a markedly reduced occurrence of wound complications and subsequent surgical interventions. The researchers determined that the minimally invasive technique was an effective strategy for addressing intra-articular calcaneal fractures.²³

Subtalar joint arthritis, a known long-term complication of intra-articular calcaneal fractures, was noted in both groups but was slightly higher in the ELA group. This may be related to the degree of articular surface damage and possibly delayed rehabilitation due to wound issues.

Despite its advantages, the Sinus Tarsi Approach is not without limitations. Its restricted view can reduce more complex fracture patterns that are technically demanding, and proper preoperative planning and intraoperative fluoroscopic guidance are essential. Surgeon experience also plays a vital role in ensuring optimal outcomes with either approach.

Conclusions:

This study highlights that both the Sinus Tarsi Approach (STA) and the Extensile Lateral Approach (ELA) are effective in restoring anatomical alignment and achieving satisfactory functional outcomes in displaced intra-articular calcaneal fractures. However, the Sinus Tarsi Approach demonstrated clear advantages in terms of reduced soft tissue complications, shorter operative time, and faster postoperative recovery. While ELA offers better visualization for complex fracture patterns, it is associated with a higher risk of wound healing issues. Therefore, the Sinus Tarsi Approach can be considered a safer and less invasive alternative for selected cases, especially where soft tissue preservation is a priority. Proper patient selection and surgical expertise remain key factors in optimizing outcomes with either technique.

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